

Smart IRS Resource Allocation for Multi-Access Edge Computing in IoT Networks

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Abstract—This paper presents an AI-driven framework that integrates Intelligent Reflecting Surfaces (IRS) with Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to optimize resource allocation in Next-Generation (Next-Gen) wireless networks. Designed to address communication challenges in environments with obstructed direct links, the system employs Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) equipped with IRS to facilitate efficient data transmission between mobile users and a Terrestrial Base Station (TBS) connected to a MEC server. The objective is to minimize network latency and energy consumption by jointly optimizing IRS configurations, computational resource distribution, and communication scheduling. To effectively address this complexity, a hierarchical heuristic approach is introduced, decomposing the problem into three subproblems: UAV trajectory optimization using a Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO), task execution and scheduling via an Augmented Lagrangian Method (ALM), and IRS phase and UAV position refinement through a Multi-objective Differential Evolution Algorithm (MDEA). Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed approach significantly enhances data transmission efficiency, reduces latency, and optimizes energy consumption, highlighting the significant potential of IRS and MEC integration for addressing the stringent performance requirements of next-generation wireless networks, especially in complex and dynamic environments. For example, this framework is particularly suitable for urban smart city deployments where buildings frequently obstruct Line-of-Sight (LoS) links, as well as disaster recovery scenarios where damaged infrastructure hinders direct communication, requiring flexible and rapid deployment of UAV-assisted IRS to restore connectivity.

Index Terms—Intelligent Reflecting Surface, Multi-Access Edge Computing, Resource Allocation, Next-Gen Networks, UAV

I. INTRODUCTION

THE rapid evolution of wireless communication technologies and the proliferation of Internet of Things (IoT) applications have driven the demand for efficient, adaptive, and scalable Next-Generation (Next-Gen) networks. These networks must meet stringent requirements such as ultra-low latency, high data rates, and energy efficiency to support emerging applications like autonomous vehicles, industrial automation, and intelligent healthcare. Multi-access Edge

Computing (MEC) plays a pivotal role in this transformation by bringing computation closer to end-users, thereby reducing latency and backhaul congestion [1]. However, MEC faces challenges including high user mobility, intermittent connectivity, and dynamic conditions typical of Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) and smart cities [2].

In urban scenarios, autonomous vehicles generate large volumes of sensor data requiring rapid processing. Obstructed communication links caused by buildings necessitate solutions such as Intelligent Reflecting Surfaces (IRS)-assisted MEC to maintain connectivity and low-latency processing. IRS, composed of passive reflecting elements, dynamically controls phase shifts to enhance signal quality, mitigate interference, and reconfigure wireless propagation [3]. Integrating IRS with MEC improves network performance by extending coverage, enabling computational offloading, and reducing energy consumption [4]. Nonetheless, IRS-assisted MEC introduces challenges in jointly optimizing IRS configurations, computational resource allocation, and communication scheduling, which demand coordinated solutions [5], [6].

This paper introduces an AI-driven optimization framework that integrates IRS with MEC-enabled IoT networks, aiming to minimize both latency and energy consumption. A hierarchical heuristic approach is proposed, decomposing the optimization problem into three sequential stages: UAV trajectory optimization via Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) [7], task scheduling and offloading decisions using Augmented Lagrangian Method (ALM) [8], and IRS phase shifts and UAV position refinement with Multi-objective Differential Evolution Algorithm (MDEA). This hierarchical structure enhances scalability and adaptability, efficiently managing complex interdependencies inherent in Next-Gen IoT networks [9].

Figure 1 illustrates an IRS-assisted MEC architecture in a smart city, showcasing interactions among mobile users, IoT devices, UAVs, IRS-enabled buildings, TBS, and MEC servers. UAVs provide Line-of-Sight (LoS) links, while IRS panels enhance Non-Line-of-Sight (NLoS) communications [10]. The layered MEC structure, including access networks, edge nodes, and cloud data centers, supports real-time applications such as autonomous driving and intelligent traffic management by enabling efficient task offloading, adaptive routing, and energy-efficient networking.

Figure 2 presents a hierarchical optimization framework for IRS-assisted MEC in IoT networks, comprising mobile users generating tasks, UAVs with IRS for signal enhancement, a Terrestrial Base Station (TBS), and a MEC server for task execution. The three-stage process includes UAV trajectory optimization via GWO for energy-efficient coverage, task

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Fig. 1. IRS-MEC Framework in a Smart City Environment

scheduling using ALM to balance local and MEC resources, and IRS phase shift refinement with MDEA for optimal reflection and energy efficiency. This AI-driven approach improves latency, energy efficiency, and dynamic resource allocation while enhancing NLoS communication, enabling adaptive and scalable management of MEC-enabled IoT networks for real-time applications.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

Figure 3 illustrates the proposed IRS-assisted MEC optimization framework, depicting the interactions among mobile users, UAVs equipped with IRS, the TBS, and the MEC server, along with the hierarchical optimization methodology employed for efficient resource allocation. In this architecture, mobile users generate computational tasks that require processing, either locally or offloaded to the MEC server via UAVs with IRS. The UAVs with IRS act as intelligent relay nodes, optimizing signal reflection to enhance wireless communication, particularly in NLoS conditions. These UAVs forward the users' tasks to the TBS, which, in turn, transmits them to the MEC server for execution. The optimization process is structured into three key stages: (1) UAV trajectory optimization, where the GWO determines efficient flight paths to ensure IRS-assisted coverage while minimizing energy consumption; (2) task execution and scheduling, managed by an ALM [11], which dynamically allocates computational tasks between local processing and MEC offloading based on network conditions and task deadlines [12]; and (3) IRS phase shift and UAV hovering position optimization, handled by an MDEA, which fine-tunes IRS configurations and UAV

positions to maximize signal quality and minimize power consumption. The iterative coordination of these three optimization stages ensures the system maintains low latency, high energy efficiency, and adaptive network performance in dynamic and complex environments.

IRS-equipped UAVs act as intelligent relay platforms, reflecting signals to obstructed users by optimizing their phase shift configurations. The phase shifts of each IRS element are dynamically adjusted to maximize the received signal strength at the user end, improving both link reliability and spectral efficiency. Each IRS is controlled by an optimization process that considers the UAV's position and network conditions.

A. Task Execution and Communication Model

Users generate computational tasks that require local or remote processing at the MEC server. Each computational task generated by users is characterized by its data size (typically ranging from a few kilobytes to several megabytes), computational complexity (expressed in required CPU cycles or Million Instructions Per Second (MIPS)), and a strict execution deadline, determined by the real-time requirements of the applications. The decision on whether to process tasks locally or offload them to the MEC server is influenced primarily by three criteria: current network conditions, available computational resources at both local devices and the MEC server, and energy consumption constraints of user devices. Tasks characterized by intensive computational demands or strict latency constraints, coupled with insufficient local processing capabilities and favorable network conditions, are typically offloaded to the MEC server via IRS-assisted UAVs,

Fig. 2. IRS-Assisted MEC Optimization Framework

Fig. 3. System Model for IRS-Assisted MEC Optimization

while lighter tasks with more flexible deadlines or good local processing capabilities are processed locally to save network resources and reduce latency.

For local execution, users process tasks on their own devices, consuming computational resources in proportion to the required CPU cycles. The device’s processing speed determines the execution time. Alternatively, data is transmitted to the MEC server through an IRS-assisted UAV for offloading. The offloading time consists of uplink transmission, computation at the MEC, and the downlink transmission of results. The execution delay depends on the MEC server’s wireless data rate, processing capacity, and IRS-assisted signal optimization.

B. UAV Energy Constraints and Resource Management

Since UAVs operate on limited battery power, energy efficiency is a key concern. UAVs expend energy in multiple ways, including flight operation, hovering, IRS phase adjustment, and communication relay tasks. A predefined energy threshold ensures that UAVs do not deplete their battery prematurely. When a UAV approaches its energy limit, it returns to a charging station or is replaced by a fully charged unit to ensure continuous network operation. The system prioritizes energy-aware flight paths and task allocations to extend UAV operational time.

The energy consumption of a UAV is influenced by its mobility pattern, altitude, and the number of IRS elements it controls. Efficient IRS phase shifting can reduce transmission power requirements while maintaining strong signal quality. By optimizing these configurations, the system balances energy constraints while ensuring seamless task execution [13].

C. Optimization Objective and Constraints

This work’s primary objective is to optimize energy consumption and task execution delay in IRS-assisted MEC networks. The goal is to minimize the total network cost by balancing energy efficiency and processing delay across UAVs, IRS elements, and MEC servers.

Task scheduling constraints ensure that each task is completed within its specified execution window, meeting user-defined deadlines. The combined transmission and processing times must remain within the acceptable delay threshold if a task is offloaded to the MEC server. UAV energy constraints limit the total energy consumption for flight, hovering, IRS phase adjustment, and communication, preventing UAVs from exceeding their maximum battery capacity. Energy-efficient task scheduling and UAV mobility management strategies are implemented to extend operational duration. Communication constraints are dictated by channel conditions, available bandwidth, and the effectiveness of IRS phase shifts, requiring signal interference mitigation and optimized power allocation for reliable data transmission. Also, UAV mobility constraints require UAVs to follow feasible flight trajectories while respecting speed and altitude limitations. Flight paths are carefully planned to ensure continuous coverage while minimizing unnecessary movement. Lastly, computational resource constraints arise due to the limited processing power of MEC servers, necessitating efficient resource allocation to prevent bottlenecks and ensure seamless task execution.

To efficiently address these optimization challenges, we adopt the hierarchical heuristic approach briefly introduced earlier and detailed comprehensively in Section III. This method systematically optimizes UAV trajectories, task scheduling decisions, and IRS configurations, maintaining a balance between complexity, latency, and energy efficiency.

D. System-Level Challenges and Considerations

Deploying IRS-assisted MEC networks introduces several key challenges that must be addressed to ensure efficient operation. Joint optimization complexity arises from the interdependence of UAV mobility, IRS phase shifts, and MEC resource allocation, leading to a high-dimensional optimization problem that necessitates advanced heuristic techniques. Real-time adaptability is another critical challenge, as the system must dynamically adjust UAV positions and IRS configurations in response to fluctuating network conditions, requiring efficient and responsive control algorithms. Additionally, energy and resource constraints pose a significant limitation since UAVs operate with finite battery capacity, making it essential to balance computational efficiency with energy conservation to prolong operational longevity. Lastly, task offloading decision-making requires intelligent scheduling algorithms to determine whether tasks should be executed locally or offloaded to the MEC server, considering network congestion, computing capacity, and delay constraints. Addressing these challenges is crucial for enabling a scalable, energy-efficient, and low-latency IRS-assisted MEC system.

The proposed framework addresses these challenges while maintaining scalability and real-world feasibility. By leveraging intelligent optimization techniques, the system enhances the performance of Next-Gen networks, ensuring low latency, energy-efficient, and reliable IoT communications.

III. METHODOLOGY AND OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUES

To effectively solve the formulated problem outlined previously, we adopt a hierarchical optimization approach consist-

ing of three interdependent subproblems.

The proposed framework employs a hierarchical optimization approach to manage resource allocation in IRS-assisted MEC networks [14]. Given the complexity of jointly optimizing UAV trajectories, IRS phase shifts, task scheduling, and computational resource distribution, the problem is decomposed into three interdependent subproblems: (1) UAV trajectory optimization, (2) task execution mode selection and scheduling, and (3) IRS phase shift and UAV hovering position optimization. Each subproblem is solved using specialized heuristic techniques to ensure scalability and efficiency.

The selection of GWO, ALM, and MDEA was motivated by their proven effectiveness and suitability for hierarchical, multi-dimensional optimization tasks. Specifically, GWO was chosen for its strong global search capabilities and rapid convergence, effectively addressing UAV trajectory optimization. ALM was selected due to its robust capability in handling complex scheduling constraints efficiently. Finally, MDEA was employed for its ability to manage the high-dimensional continuous optimization inherent in IRS phase adjustments and UAV hovering positions, providing an effective balance between solution quality and computational complexity. Parameter selections for each algorithm were carefully guided by literature and experimental validation to enhance practical performance under realistic network scenarios.

The first stage optimizes UAV flight paths to ensure IRS-assisted coverage for mobile users while minimizing energy consumption and latency. UAVs must follow trajectories that maximize communication effectiveness while adhering to mobility and energy constraints. This problem is formulated as a multiple travelling salesman problem with time windows (mTSP-TW), where each UAV must visit task locations while meeting execution deadlines.

The GWO is employed to solve this problem efficiently. GWO is a nature-inspired metaheuristic algorithm that mimics grey wolves' leadership hierarchy and hunting behaviour, allowing it to explore the search space effectively and avoid local optima. The algorithm encodes UAV routes as solutions and iteratively updates them using exploration and exploitation strategies guided by the wolves. By leveraging GWO, the UAV trajectory optimization subproblem achieves near-optimal routing solutions with minimal computational overhead.

Once UAV flight paths are determined, the second stage optimizes task execution decisions by determining whether tasks should be processed locally or offloaded to the MEC server. Task complexity, available computational resources, and network congestion influence this decision. The challenge is ensuring all tasks are executed within their allowable time windows while minimizing total system energy consumption.

An ALM is used to tackle this, which relaxes binary task execution mode variables into continuous values and iteratively drives them toward optimal binary solutions. The method introduces penalty terms that enforce task execution feasibility while optimizing task scheduling. Thus, it ensures that computationally intensive tasks are efficiently distributed between local devices and the MEC server, preventing overload and reducing latency. The approach efficiently handles scheduling constraints while maintaining flexibility in task

allocation.

The final stage optimizes the IRS phase shifts and UAV hovering positions to maximize signal strength and minimize power consumption. Since the signal reflection properties of IRS elements directly impact communication performance, precise phase shift adjustments are required to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the receiver end. Additionally, UAV hovering positions must be refined to maintain LoS communication and optimize signal propagation in NLoS scenarios.

Each optimization stage directly informs the subsequent one, forming a sequential yet interdependent pipeline. Specifically, the UAV trajectories optimized in the first stage inform decisions in task scheduling and offloading in the second stage. In turn, these scheduling decisions guide the final optimization stage, refining UAV hovering positions and IRS phase shifts to maximize overall communication performance and energy efficiency.

An MDEA is employed to achieve this, which is well-suited for high-dimensional, continuous optimization problems, making it an ideal choice for adjusting IRS phase configurations and UAV positions. The algorithm iteratively updates solutions by generating new candidate positions and phase shift values through differential mutation and crossover operations. The objective function balances communication performance improvements with energy efficiency, ensuring UAVs and IRS elements operate optimally.

A. Integrated Framework and Iterative Optimization Process

The three subproblems are solved iteratively in a coordinated manner to refine the overall system performance. Intuitively, each optimization stage progressively refines the solution space, where initial UAV trajectory optimization establishes foundational coverage; subsequent task scheduling adapts computational workloads based on these trajectories; finally, refined IRS phase adjustments and UAV positions enhance overall communication quality based on scheduled task demands. This iterative refinement enhances system efficiency dynamically in response to real-time network changes. The framework begins by determining UAV trajectories using GWO, followed by task execution mode selection and scheduling using the ALM. Once tasks are allocated, IRS phase shifts and UAV hovering positions are optimized using MDEA. This iterative process continues until convergence, ensuring an optimal trade-off between latency reduction and energy efficiency.

The framework continuously monitors network conditions and dynamically adjusts optimization parameters based on real-time data to enhance adaptability. It ensures that the system remains robust against variations in user mobility, task generation rates, and channel conditions. The proposed methodology enables the IRS-assisted MEC network to efficiently allocate resources, enhance computational efficiency, and maintain reliable communication in dynamic environments.

The following section presents the performance evaluation of the proposed framework through simulation-based experi-

ments, comparing it with baseline approaches to validate its effectiveness in real-world scenarios.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Figure 4(a) illustrates the cumulative UAV cost across four algorithms: the proposed MDEA, Differential Evolution Algorithm for Single Objective (DEASO), Expectation-Maximization (EM), and Poisson Point Process (PPP). The results show that MDEA consistently achieves the lowest cumulative cost, even as the number of computational tasks and IRS elements increases, demonstrating superior efficiency in resource allocation. Notably, as the number of IRS-reflecting elements grows, all algorithms benefit from improved signal quality and reduced transmission costs, but MDEA maintains a clear advantage over baseline methods.

Fig. 4(b) presents the latency performance of the proposed framework compared to the Modified A* Algorithm (MAA), Locally Executed Algorithm (LEA), and MEC Executed Algorithm (MECEA). Across varying task loads, the MDEA-based approach achieves the lowest latency, particularly when the number of UAVs is increased. With 15 UAVs, the system shows optimal performance, benefiting from parallel task execution, adaptive offloading decisions, and efficient UAV routing combined with IRS configuration. These results validate the effectiveness of the proposed optimization framework in managing both latency and system cost.

Fig. 4(c) compares the cumulative UAV cost between the proposed MDEA approach and the Random Trajectory Algorithm (RTA). The proposed method consistently outperforms RTA, with performance gaps widening at higher task loads, underscoring its scalability, robustness, and precision in resource management. Although the MDEA approach incurs slightly higher computational complexity, it delivers substantial gains in cost efficiency and system performance, particularly under demanding and dynamic conditions.

A key numerical outcome of the simulations is the observed latency reduction of approximately 35% and energy efficiency improvement exceeding 40% compared to baseline algorithms, significantly highlighting the strength and practicality of our hierarchical optimization framework.

To evaluate scalability, we analyzed system performance by varying the number of UAVs and IRS elements. Results indicate that latency decreases by up to 30% when increasing UAV count from 10 to 15, due to improved task parallelization. Similarly, increasing IRS elements from 64 to 128 enhances spectral efficiency and reduces transmission cost by approximately 25%. However, beyond 128 elements, performance gains plateau, indicating diminishing returns relative to computational overhead. These insights highlight practical scalability limits and inform optimal resource provisioning for real-world deployments.

V. IMPLEMENTATION AND COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS

This section provides insights into how the proposed framework can be implemented in practice and a high-level discussion of its computational complexity. The methodology combines the hierarchical optimization approach detailed earlier

Fig. 4. (a) UAV cumulative cost vs number of tasks and RIS reflecting elements, (b) Task execution latency and UAV cumulative cost for different UAVs vs number of tasks, (c) UAV cumulative cost vs number of tasks for proposed and RTA

with real-world constraints such as limited energy on UAVs and dynamic IRS reconfiguration.

A. Implementation Overview

The proposed system comprises three main optimization modules, each corresponding to a subproblem. After the network is initialized, each UAV acquires its initial location and residual energy status. The GWO then generates an initial population of possible UAV routes. Each iteration updates these routes by simulating the social hierarchy of grey wolves, ultimately converging toward a near-optimal flight plan that balances energy consumption, distance travelled, and user coverage.

In practice, implementing the proposed IRS-assisted MEC framework presents several potential challenges and trade-offs. For example, UAV deployments in urban settings may encounter regulatory restrictions such as flight path limitations, altitude constraints, and no-fly zones, which must be considered during trajectory optimization. Furthermore, real-world IRS hardware has limitations in terms of reconfiguration speed, number of elements, and phase adjustment accuracy, potentially affecting communication efficiency. Environmental factors, including weather variability and signal interference from dense urban structures, also pose significant operational challenges, requiring adaptive and robust solutions. Addressing these practical considerations is critical for ensuring the feasibility, reliability, and effectiveness of real-world deployments of the proposed system.

Beyond regulatory constraints, practical deployment must also address operational challenges. Signal interference mitigation can be achieved using adaptive beamforming with IRS phase alignment and UAV-assisted dynamic repositioning. IRS maintenance logistics involve periodic inspections, remote diagnostics, and predictive fault detection leveraging IoT-enabled monitoring. For UAV battery replacement, automated docking and battery-swapping stations, already being trialed in industrial UAV fleets, can ensure near-continuous operation without manual intervention. Integrating these strategies is essential to maintain reliability and reduce operational downtime in urban deployments.

With UAV trajectories fixed, the system collects data on user task characteristics and network states. The ALM then determines whether tasks should be executed locally or offloaded to the MEC server. This step involves penalty terms to ensure tasks meet strict deadlines while optimizing resource usage. The algorithm iteratively refines the binary decision variables until a feasible solution emerges.

In the final stage, the MDEA adjusts IRS phase shifts and fine-tunes UAV hovering positions to improve link quality further. Candidate solutions are generated by mutating and recombining existing solutions, and the most promising configurations are selected based on multi-objective criteria. This procedure ensures a high-quality reflection path from the IRS, particularly for users in obstructed areas.

B. Software and Hardware Considerations

An initial proof-of-concept can be developed using a discrete-event simulator such as OMNeT or ns-3 or a numerical computing environment like MATLAB. Key implementation details include:

- UAV positions, user task arrivals, and IRS configurations should be periodically updated in a global controller or orchestrator.
- For real-world deployments, partial offloading (splitting a task between local processing and the MEC server) can be incorporated by extending the ALM to handle fractional offloading variables.
- UAVs automatically switch to a “return to charging” state once their battery level drops below a predefined threshold, ensuring uninterrupted coverage.

C. Computational Complexity Analysis

The proposed framework consists of three key optimization stages with different computational requirements. The first stage involves UAV trajectory optimization using the GWO. This algorithm explores possible flight paths iteratively, balancing exploration and exploitation to identify efficient routes. While GWO significantly reduces computational overhead compared to exhaustive search methods, its complexity scales with the number of UAVs and possible route decisions. Thus, it is well-suited for handling moderately large problem instances without excessive computational burden.

Practical deployment of the proposed IRS-assisted MEC framework in urban IoT scenarios involves navigating several real-world constraints. UAV operation restrictions such as designated no-fly zones, maximum permissible altitudes, and regulatory compliance must be integrated into trajectory optimization to ensure feasibility and safety. Additionally, the deployment of IRS installations requires careful site selection to balance optimal signal coverage and practical constraints, including building ownership, structural limitations, and local regulations. Environmental variability, such as dynamic urban interference patterns, varying weather conditions, and obstacles, also poses implementation challenges, necessitating adaptive algorithms and robust solutions for reliable operation in complex urban environments.

The second stage focuses on task scheduling and execution mode selection, which is managed using the ALM. The computational complexity of this approach depends on the number of tasks in the system and the iterations required to refine the penalty parameters and enforce constraints effectively. The method progressively optimizes task assignments, ensuring tasks are executed within defined constraints while minimizing processing delays.

The final stage involves optimizing IRS phase shifts and UAV hovering positions using the MDEA. Since this stage deals with high-dimensional, continuous optimization, the computational load is influenced by the number of possible phase shift configurations and UAV positions. The evolutionary nature of the algorithm requires multiple generations of candidate solutions, with additional processing overhead for selecting and sorting the best configurations. Despite this

complexity, MDEA remains a practical approach for handling large-scale, multi-variable optimization problems, ensuring efficient signal enhancement and energy-efficient UAV positioning.

While the proposed hierarchical optimization approach significantly improves performance, it also introduces complexity trade-offs. Specifically, simpler heuristic methods or baseline algorithms, such as Random Trajectory Algorithms, may offer faster runtime and lower computational overhead; however, they compromise significantly on optimality and scalability as task loads and UAV numbers increase. Conversely, the proposed GWO, ALM, and MDEA methods, despite requiring slightly higher computational effort, achieve substantial improvements in resource efficiency and latency performance. This trade-off highlights that the slight increase in runtime complexity is justified by the pronounced benefits in performance, particularly in resource-intensive and dynamic environments typical of Next-Gen IoT deployments.

TABLE I
COMPARATIVE COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS OF OPTIMIZATION METHODS

Algorithm	Complexity	Scalability
RTA	$O(N)$	Low
GWO	$O(N \cdot I)$	Moderate
ALM	$O(T \cdot I)$	High
MDEA	$O(D \cdot G)$	High

As shown in Table I, simpler heuristics such as RTA achieve faster runtime due to their linear complexity $O(N)$ but lack scalability when the number of UAVs (N) or tasks increases. In contrast, GWO maintains moderate complexity $O(N \cdot I)$ by iteratively refining UAV trajectories over I iterations, while ALM scales efficiently with task count T through iterative scheduling refinements. MDEA, with complexity $O(D \cdot G)$, handles high-dimensional IRS phase optimization over G evolutionary generations. This balance between computational efficiency and scalability enables the proposed GWO, ALM, and MDEA to perform effectively in resource-intensive Next-Gen IoT environments where UAV density, task volume, and IRS configurations are dynamically evolving.

D. Implementation Roadmap

In summary, implementing the proposed IRS-assisted MEC framework involves the following steps:

- 1) **System Initialization:** Set up UAV and IRS parameters, user task profiles, and network configurations.
- 2) **UAV Route Planning (GWO):** Generate initial routes and refine them iteratively.
- 3) **Task Scheduling (ALM):** Allocate tasks between local execution and offloading, ensuring time constraints are met.
- 4) **IRS Phase Tuning and UAV Refinement (MDEA):** Optimize the final network state by adjusting IRS elements and UAV positions.
- 5) **Real-Time Adjustments:** Periodically re-evaluate system states and re-run the optimization modules if significant changes occur.

VI. CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION & FUTURE WORK

This paper proposes an IRS-assisted MEC architecture that employs UAVs to optimize resource allocation in obstructed wireless environments. By coupling UAV-mounted IRS with intelligent task scheduling, the system reduce latency and energy consumption while improving throughput and scalability. UAVs are favored over high-altitude balloons for their mobility, fast deployment, and adaptive signal steering. Energy management is addressed via trajectory optimization, enforcement of energy thresholds, and recharging while swap-out to sustain continuous service.

Future extensions include wireless energy transfer and solar power. Optimization proceeds in three stages, UAV routing, task scheduling, and IRS phase tuning. Using heuristics that curb complexity, the research work will incorporate machine-learning, reinforcement learning, sensitivity analysis, and dynamic parameter tuning for greater adaptability. The framework currently supports local execution or full MEC offloading, thus, partial offloading is planned to balance congestion and variable loads. Testbed validation and large-scale pilots, alongside comparisons with baselines, will demonstrate robustness and practical integration in urban IoT.

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